

Report:

A2.1.5

Deliverable D3: "Validation report on the primary standards developed for the in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity of Newtonian liquids with a target uncertainty of 2 % (k=2)"

This report was written as part of activity 2.1.5 from the EMPIR Metrology for Drug Delivery (MeDD II) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2019 and focused on providing traceable measurements of volume, flow and pressure of existing drug delivery devices and mixing behavior and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems. For more details about this project, please visit www.drugmetrology.com

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Introduction to the EMPIR Metrology for Drug Delivery project

The overall aim of this project is to improve dosing accuracy and to enable the traceable measurement of volume, flow and pressure in existing drug delivery devices and in-line sensors operating at very low flow rates. This will be achieved through the development of new calibration methods and by expanding the existing metrological infrastructure. This project will also investigate fast changing flow rates, which are step changes between two flow rates within a second, the physical properties of mixtures of liquids and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems in order to prevent inaccurate measurement results and thus to improve patient safety.

The specific objectives of the project are:

1. To develop new traceable techniques for generating and measuring the response or delay time of drug delivery devices regarding changes in flow rate, from 5 nL/min to 100 nL/min, using Newtonian liquids (WP1). For steady flow rates an uncertainty of 1 % ($k=2$) or better is expected, whereas for fast changing flow rates an uncertainty of 2 % ($k=2$) or better is expected. The techniques developed will be used to characterise and validate the different response times of at least 3 different types of drug delivery devices (including infusion analysers) (WP3 and WP4) and one type of flow sensor, to accurately measure the administered flow and volume with the required uncertainties.
2. To upgrade the existing flow facilities and knowledge of the partner NMIs in order to enable the traceable in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity of Newtonian liquids, as a function of the flow rate and pressure difference, with a target uncertainty value of 2 % ($k=2$). The measurement uncertainty will be validated using Newtonian liquids with traceable dynamic viscosity calibration. Additionally, tests with non-Newtonian liquids will be performed in order to prove the concept. To calibrate transfer standards for the in-line measurement of dynamic viscosity and other physical properties of liquids, in order to use these transfer standards for flow measurement and to determine the mixing behaviour of different liquids.
3. To develop and validate novel calibration procedures for existing medical flow devices (e.g. infusion pumps, pain controllers and infusion pump analysers) with traceability to a primary standard and with a target uncertainty value of 2 % ($k=2$) for a range of 5 nL/min up to 600 ml/min and also to develop a proof-of-concept on-chip microfluidic pump used as a transfer standard in drug discovery and organ-on-a-chip applications for flow rates lower than 100 nL/min.
4. To design and develop a multi-infusion system containing check valves, with several options for testing how liquids, with different viscosities mix and flow and how this affects drug concentration. The flow rates and pressures will be traceably calibrated in all infusion lines, as well as at the outlet of the syringe pump, to be able to analyse the effects of pressure-equalising devices and to detect occlusion phenomena and bad mixing configurations.
5. To facilitate the take up of the technology and measurement infrastructure developed in the project by the measurement supply chain (i.e. accredited laboratories, instrumentation manufacturers, etc.), standards developing organisations (ISO/TC 30, ISO/TC 48, ISO/TC/SC 62D, ISO/TC 69, ISO/TC 76, ISO/TC 84, ISO/TC 150, ISO/TC 210) and end-users (i.e. hospitals and health centres).

Activity 2.1.5 – validation report on the primary standards developed for the in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity of Newtonian liquids

Overall Objective: Using input from A2.1.1-A2.1.4, RISE, METAS, NEL and NQIS will write a validation report on the primary standards developed for the in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity of Newtonian liquids with a target uncertainty of 2 % (k=2).

Once agreed by the consortium, the coordinator will then submit the validation report to EURAMET as **D3**: 'Validation report on the primary standards developed for the in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity of Newtonian liquids with a target uncertainty of 2 % (k=2)'.

The following Institutes have contributed to this Deliverable:

no	Participant Type	Short Name	Organisation legal full name	Country
1	Internal Funded Partner	IPQ	Instituto Português da Qualidade, I.P.	Portugal
5	Internal Funded Partner	METAS	Eidgenössisches Institut für Metrologie METAS	Switzerland
6	Internal Funded Partner	NEL	TUV SUD Limited	United Kingdom
7	Internal Funded Partner	NQIS	National Quality Infrastructure System	Greece
8	Internal Funded Partner	RISE	RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB	Sweden
10	External Funded Partner	HSG-MIT	Hahn-Schickard-Gesellschaft für angewandte Forschung e.V.	Germany
16	Unfunded Partner	KRISS	Korea Research Institute of Standards and Science	Republic of Korea

The progress within this report covers the Period from 1st June 2019 to the end of August 2022.

1 Introduction

Capillary glass viscometers are widely used and their method is well established worldwide for traceable measurement of the kinematic viscosity to the SI units. However, this technique does not allow in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity in flow applications, which is important for the process-oriented information about the dynamic viscosity of the liquid. The micro pipe viscometers enable the characterization of liquids under flow conditions and the direct calibration of devices that measure dynamic viscosity under flow conditions or investigation of the influence of dynamic viscosity on the performance of flow devices.

This report describes the primary standards developed by NEL, RISE and METAS based on micro pipe viscometers for the in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosities. Their stated measurement uncertainties have been validated by the measurements of the dynamic viscosity of the liquids A – H and their consistency has been demonstrated in this report.

2 Primary standards developed for the in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity of Newtonian liquids

The primary standards developed by METAS, NEL and RISE for the in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity of Newtonian liquids are described in this chapter. The measurement principle is the pipe viscometer, where all the dimensional parameters as well as all sensors for pressure, temperature and flow rate are calibrated to ensure traceability to SI units.

2.1 Working principle of a micro pipe viscometer

The micro pipe viscometer consists of a flow generator (piston prover) connected to a tube. Appropriate temperature and pressure sensors are installed upstream and downstream of the micro tube, which finally ends in a liquid collecting reservoir as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic setup of the micro pipe viscometer with a flow generator (piston prover), temperature and pressure sensors upstream and downstream of the micro tube.

For the laminar flow regime and a straight channel, the Hagen-Poiseuille law describes the relation between the pressure drop, the flow rate, the dynamic viscosity, the length and the inner diameter of the micro tube. This law has been applied to indirectly determine the inner diameter of the micro tube by measuring the pressure drop for a given range of known flow rates with a liquid of known and traceable viscosity. The inner radius r of the micro tube can then be determined according to equation (1) of the Hagen-Poiseuille law:

$$r = \sqrt[4]{\frac{8 \cdot \eta \cdot Q \cdot L}{\pi \cdot \Delta P}} \quad (1)$$

where η is the dynamic viscosity, ΔP is the pressure drop over the micro tube, Q is the volumetric flow rate, L is the length of the micro tube.

In this case, water was used as the reference liquid. The accurate measurement of the water temperature allows the calculation of the dynamic viscosity according to the NIST database for water properties [1]. The validation of the micro pipe viscometer has been performed by calibrating the dynamic viscosity of various Newtonian liquids, which have been also calibrated by other laboratories using micro pipe viscometers and viscosity measuring instruments. These results are presented later in this report.

Three National Metrology Institutes (NMI) have developed a micro pipe viscometer at their flow facility, which are described in the following sections. Further details can be found in report A2.1.3.

2.2 Micro pipe viscometer at METAS

The flow facility at METAS [2-4] has currently been extended to include a section with a micro pipe viscometer, as can be seen in Figure 2. The pipe viscometer consists of a piston prover to generate the flow and a micro tube with upstream and downstream temperature and pressure sensors. The tubing connected to the pressure sensor and the connectors to the micro tube have much larger diameters (more than 2 mm) than the nominal inner diameter of the micro tubes of 0.13 mm to ensure that the recorded pressure drop between the two pressure sensors is essentially due to the pressure drop over the micro tube. Flow rates from 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ to 150 mL/min can be generated for the in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity with a pressure drop up to 10 bar. Glass micro tubes with larger inner diameter are also available, but the measurement results presented here have been obtained with the glass micro tube with the inner diameter of 0.13 mm.

The expanded uncertainty $U(k=2)$ of the dynamic viscosity measurement is 0.90 %.

Figure 2: The micro pipe viscometer at METAS: (A) piston prover, (B) temperature sensors, (C) pressure sensors and (D) the glass micro tube with an inner diameter of 0.13 mm and a length of 200 mm.

The inner diameter of the glass micro tube is the most challenging measurement for the traceability of the micro pipe viscometer. Therefore, two methods have been applied at METAS to determine this inner diameter: both by means of the $\mu\text{-CT}$ facility operated at METAS [5] and the flow characterization method according to the Hagen-Poiseuille law described above. Both methods lead to consistent

results within the corresponding measurement uncertainty for the inner diameter of the glass micro tube.

Knowing all the geometrical characteristics of the micro glass tube, the micro pipe viscometer has been validated by calibrating traceable reference liquids for dynamic viscosity. A detailed description of the investigations and the validation of the expanded uncertainty can be found in [6].

Table 1: Validation of the results and the stated uncertainty of the micro pipe viscometer with reference liquids for traceable dynamic viscosity [7].

Reference liquid name	Temperature (°C)	Reference dynamic viscosity (mPa·s)	Dynamic viscosity with glass micro pipe viscometer (mPa·s)	Deviation (%)	Expanded uncertainty (%)
2AW	21.3	1.5319 ± 0.0031	1.538 ± 0.014	+0.43	0.90
2BW	21.3	2.1913 ± 0.0044	2.201 ± 0.020	+0.42	0.90
5AW	21.3	4.0393 ± 0.0081	4.056 ± 0.037	+0.42	0.90

2.3 Micro pipe viscometer at RISE

The micro pipe viscometer at RISE consists of a capillary holder and an associated stainless steel micro tube with a nominal inner diameter of 0.18 mm, an outer diameter of 1/16" and a length of 300 mm. The pressure drop is measured by pressure sensors upstream and downstream of the micro tube at pressures up to 5 bar (Figure 3). The temperature of the test liquid is measured indirectly with two type K thermocouples attached to the inlet and outlet of the capillary holder. The desired flow rate is generated using a syringe pump and calibrated syringes. To account for the pressure loss in all connections, additional measurements have been performed using a micro tube with the same inner diameter but a shorter length of 50 mm. The expanded uncertainty $U(k=2)$ of the dynamic viscosity measurement is 2.0% [8].

Figure 3: The micro pipe viscometer at RISE with pre-cut stainless steel micro tubes with a length of 50 mm and 300 mm.

2.4 Micro pipe viscometer at NEL

The micro pipe viscometer at NEL is shown in Figure 4. The calibrated syringe pump generates traceable flow rates and the Coriolis meter provides secondary flow rate indication, fluid density information as well as the identification of any bubbles or flow disturbances. Two temperature sensors (upstream and downstream sensors) are attached to the outside of the stainless-steel capillaries and used to determine the average fluid temperature. Two calibrated Elveflow pressure sensors (1 bar and 340 mbar) are directly connected to the capillaries to measure the pressure drop.

The expanded uncertainty $U(k=2)$ of the dynamic viscosity measurement is 1.0 %.

Figure 4: NEL pipe viscometer with a stainless-steel micro-tube with outer diameter of 1/16 inch (1.6 mm), length of 100 mm and nominal inner diameter of 180 μm (manufacturer's specification).

2.5 Uncertainty analysis of the micro pipe viscometer

As explained earlier, the inner diameter of the micro tube has been determined by the flow characterization method according to the Hagen-Poiseuille law, which consists of measuring the pressure drops for a given flow rate range with water whose dynamic viscosity can be calculated based on the measured water temperature using published data on water properties [1]. The uncertainty contributions of this method are as follows:

- flow generation by the piston prover / syringe pump
- length measurement of the micro tube
- pressure measurement to determine the pressure drop over the micro tube
- contribution of the tubing and connections between the pressure sensors and the micro tube to the pressure drop
- calculation of the dynamic viscosity of water by measuring the temperature of the water including the uncertainty of the temperature measurement and the uncertainty contribution from the formula for the calculated dynamic viscosity

The contributions listed above are the most important contributions to the uncertainty. Obviously, the stability of the temperature, any temperature gradient along the system and the stability of the pressure drop and the flow rate are important. If any of these stabilities are affected by the measurement method, their contributions must be evaluated and taken into account when estimating the total uncertainty.

Once the geometrical characteristics of the micro tube are determined, the measurements with the micro pipe viscometer are traceable assuming the pressure, flow rate and temperature measurements are traceable.

The uncertainty contributions of the micro pipe viscometer are listed below:

- flow generation by the piston prover / syringe pump
- length measurement of the micro tube
- inner diameter of the micro tube
- pressure measurement to determine the pressure drop over the micro tube
- pressure drop contribution of the tubing and connectors between the pressure sensors and the micro tube
- temperature measurement
- single point analysis at each flow rate for a given pressure drop compared to linear regression over the flow rate range

The latter contribution to the measurement uncertainty is related to the fact that often only one flow rate is generated and the corresponding pressure drop and the temperature are measured. However, measurements at three or four flow rates allow to test the laminar flow regime and the applicability of the Hagen-Poiseuille law to determine the dynamic viscosity of the Newtonian liquid. Three or four results of the pressure drop as a function of the flow rate allow to determine the slope of the line, where the intercept of the fit is forced to be zero. It is obvious that the linear regression method is the most accurate for determining dynamic viscosity. But any data point relating the pressure drop to the flow rate allows the dynamic viscosity to be determined as a single point analysis, and in previous research it has been shown that the single point analysis gives as consistent results as the linear regression method [6].

Details of the measurement uncertainty calculation of each pipe viscometer can be found in the report A2.1.3 and in the references [6] and [8].

3 Liquids used for the validation of the pipe viscometers

To validate the stated uncertainties of the micro pipe viscometers, eight liquids were prepared by IPQ. The dynamic viscosity of these liquids has been determined using the newly developed micro pipe viscometers and by several other laboratories using their existing instruments or methods, which are described in the next section. Each laboratory was provided with a 500 mL bottle of each liquid produced in one batch to ensure the same composition in each bottle. In addition, the density of the liquids was also measured, as some instruments measure the kinematic viscosity, which can be converted into the dynamic viscosity with the knowledge of the density of the liquid.

The compositions of the eight liquids are listed below:

- **Liquid A:** Saline solution of 0.9 %wt NaCl
- **Liquid B:** Glucose solution 10 %wt
- **Liquid C:** Glucose solution 20 %wt
- **Liquid D:** solution of NaCl 0.22 %wt and Glucose 2.75 %wt

- **Liquid E:** solution of NaCl 0.22 %wt and Glucose 5.55 %wt
- **Liquid F:** solution of NaCl 0.45 %wt and Glucose 5.54 %wt
- **Liquid G:** solution of Glycerol 52.0 %wt
- **Liquid H:** solution of Glycerol 58.8 %wt

The pipe viscometers are set up in laboratories and only the ambient temperature is controlled and kept constant. To compare the results of the dynamic viscosity of different laboratories, the temperature dependence of the density and the dynamic viscosity of the liquids A – H must be known. The reference temperature has been defined at 22.0 °C, which is close to the ambient temperature of all laboratories. Thus, the dynamic viscosity measured at ambient temperature can be corrected for the offset and the dynamic viscosity can be calculated at the reference temperature for all laboratories. The measurements of the temperature dependence of the density and the dynamic viscosity are described in the following sections and details can be found in the report A2.1.2.

3.1 Temperature dependence of the density of the liquids A – H

IPQ has measured the density of the eight liquids A – H in the temperature range from 20 °C to 30 °C and determined the coefficients of a second degree polynomial, which are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Density of the liquids A – H. Coefficients of the fitting of a 2nd degree polynomial for the temperature dependence between 20 °C and 30 °C.

Liquid	$\rho, 20\text{ °C}$ / [g·cm ⁻³]	$U_{\rho, 20\text{ °C}}$ / [g·cm ⁻³]	$\rho, 30\text{ °C}$ / [g·cm ⁻³]	Coefficients of a 2 nd degree polynomial			$U_{\rho, \text{pol. [20-30] °C}}$
				$\rho(t) = a t^2 + b t + c$			
				a / [g·cm ⁻³ ·°C ⁻²]	b / [g·cm ⁻³ ·°C]	c / [g·cm ⁻³]	
A	1.004638	3.3E-05	1.001940	-4.58242E-06	-4.07711E-05	1.007287	3.3E-05
B	1.038717	3.3E-05	1.035660	-4.01057E-06	-1.05289E-04	1.042428	3.3E-05
C	1.080480	3.3E-05	1.076951	-3.39933E-06	-1.83126E-04	1.085503	3.3E-05
D	1.010837	3.3E-05	1.008098	-4.50791E-06	-4.86868E-05	1.013615	3.3E-05
E	1.020720	3.3E-05	1.017864	-4.23734E-06	-7.38977E-05	1.023894	3.3E-05
F	1.022391	3.3E-05	1.019501	-4.26428E-06	-7.58741E-05	1.025615	3.3E-05
G	1.132333	3.3E-05	1.127058	-1.52705E-06	-4.51312E-04	1.141971	3.3E-05
H	1.151274	4.2E-05	1.145746	-1.43700E-06	-4.80843E-04	1.161466	4.2E-05

The polynomial fit allows to calculate the density as a function of temperature at 20 °C, 21 °C, 22 °C, 23 °C, 24 °C, 27 °C and 30 °C with an uncertainty of 0.004 %, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Density of the liquids A – H between 20 °C and 30 °C in the unit g/cm³.

T(°C)	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
20	1.004639	1.038718	1.080481	1.010838	1.020721	1.022392	1.132334	1.151274
21	1.004410	1.038448	1.080158	1.010605	1.020473	1.022141	1.131820	1.150735
22	1.004172	1.038171	1.079829	1.010362	1.020217	1.021882	1.131303	1.150192
23	1.003925	1.037885	1.079493	1.010111	1.019953	1.021614	1.130783	1.149646
24	1.003669	1.037591	1.079150	1.009850	1.019680	1.021338	1.130260	1.149098
27	1.002846	1.036661	1.078080	1.009014	1.018810	1.020458	1.128672	1.147436
30	1.001940	1.035660	1.076950	1.008097	1.017863	1.019501	1.127057	1.145747

3.2 Temperature dependence of the dynamic viscosity of the liquids A - H

The measurements were performed at EIM/NQIS with a TAMSON TV2000 AKV Automated Kinematic Viscosity system, where the result is the kinematic viscosity (Table 4).

Table 4: Kinematic viscosity of the liquids A – H between 20 °C and 27 °C in the unit mm²/s.

T(°C)	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
20	1.01532	1.29856	1.7844	1.0877	1.15276	1.1504	6.04426	8.89602
21	0.99368	1.26662	1.73498	1.06308	1.12436	1.1223	5.80834	8.54828
22	0.96812	1.23276	1.68796	1.03742	1.0972	1.0952	5.5948	8.17676
23	0.94712	1.20424	1.64302	1.01254	1.0718	1.0696	5.39682	7.8596
24	0.92808	1.17572	1.59974	0.9889	1.04662	1.04444	5.19756	7.54642
27	0.8659	1.09426	1.47946	0.92576	0.97624	0.979	4.66864	6.70968

To convert these values into dynamic viscosity the density values measured at IPQ were taken into account. The results have an estimated uncertainty $u(k=1)$ of 1 % (Table 5).

Table 5: Dynamic viscosity of the liquids A – H between 20 °C and 27 °C in the unit mPa·s.

T(°C)	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
20	1.0200	1.3488	1.9280	1.0995	1.1766	1.1762	6.8441	10.2418
21	0.9981	1.3153	1.8741	1.0744	1.1474	1.1471	6.5740	9.8368
22	0.9722	1.2798	1.8227	1.0482	1.1194	1.1192	6.3294	9.4048
23	0.9508	1.2499	1.7736	1.0228	1.0932	1.0927	6.1026	9.0358
24	0.9315	1.2199	1.7264	0.9986	1.0672	1.0667	5.8746	8.6716
27	0.8684	1.1344	1.5950	0.9341	0.9946	0.9990	5.2694	7.6989

4 Laboratory equipment for the measurement of dynamic viscosity and density

The laboratories used the following existing instruments or methods for the measurements of the dynamic viscosity and density of these liquids:

- **METAS, RISE and NEL:** micro pipe viscometer (described above and in more detail in report A2.1.3).
- **NQIS/EIM:** The kinematic viscosity of the liquids was measured at 20 °C, 21 °C, 22 °C, 23 °C, 24 °C and 27 °C using a TAMSON TV2000 AKV Automated Kinematic Viscosity system. The system consists of a thermostatic bath and a measuring unit. The viscosity measurements were performed using several calibrated Cannon-Fenske glass viscometers. For each temperature, five repeated measurements were performed for each liquid. The measurement procedure applied conforms to the ASTM D445 method. The uncertainty of the kinematic viscosity values obtained is estimated to be 1%. The dynamic viscosity values were calculated using the corresponding density values of the liquids measured by IPQ.
- **IPQ:** The kinematic viscosity measurements have been performed with capillary glass viscosity meters at 20 °C, 21 °C, 22 °C, 23 °C, 24 °C, 27 °C and 30 °C. The density of the liquids has been measured with an oscillation-type density meter (DMA 5000, Anton Paar) at 20 °C, 21 °C, 22 °C, 23 °C, 24 °C, 27 °C and 30 °C. The dynamic viscosity has been calculated as the product of the kinematic viscosity and the density.
- **Hahn-Schickard:** The dynamic viscosity has been measured with the rotary rheometer Physica MCR 101 from Anton Paar (Software RHEOPLUS/32 V3.40) using the CP50-1 measurement cone at a constant shear rate of 200 1/s. The viscosity measurements were performed at room temperature and the exact temperature value was recorded with a thermometer before each measurement. For each measurement run, 100 µl of the liquid was added and 20 data points were recorded at 6 s intervals. Three measurement runs were performed for each liquid.
- **KRISS:** The density was measured using an Anton Paar DMA 5000M (oscillating U-tube sensor) Measurements were performed three times on one sample and temperature ramps were performed at 1 °C interval from 20 °C to 30 °C. The kinematic viscosity was measured using capillary glass viscosity meters at 22 °C. The capillary glass viscosity meter used is a KRISS viscosity standard system. The dynamic viscosity was calculated as the product of the measured kinematic viscosity and the measured density.

5 Validation of the pipe viscometers by means of measuring the dynamic viscosity of the liquids A – H

5.1 Procedure to convert all the results to the reference temperature of 22 °C

The laboratories determined either the dynamic viscosity and/or the kinematic viscosity of the liquids and two laboratories determined the density of the liquids. As the measurements with the micro pipe viscometers determine the dynamic viscosity, the results of the laboratories that determined the kinematic viscosity were converted to the dynamic viscosity using the density values of the liquids determined by IPQ (Table 6). NQIS/EIM and IPQ carried out measurements at different temperatures, namely 20 °C, 21 °C, 22 °C, 23 °C, 24 °C, and 27 °C (report A2.1.2). These dynamic viscosity measurements were used to determine the interpolation factors for temperatures between 22 °C and 24 °C, which cover the temperatures of the measurements of the other laboratories and allow the

interpolation of the individual results to 22 °C. KRISS measured the kinematic viscosity and the density and calculated the dynamic viscosity with their own values.

5.2 Results of the density of the liquids A – H at 22 °C

The results of the densities of the liquids A – H measured at 22 °C by IPQ and KRISS are listed in Table 6.

Table 6. Density measured by the laboratories IPQ and KRISS at a temperature of 22 °C in the unit kg/m³. The results presented are the values including the expanded measurement uncertainty U(k=2).

	Liquid A	Liquid B	Liquid C	Liquid D	Liquid E	Liquid F	Liquid G	Liquid H
IPQ	1004.172 ± 0.033	1038.171 ± 0.033	1079.829 ± 0.033	1010.362 ± 0.033	1020.217 ± 0.033	1021.882 ± 0.033	1131.303 ± 0.033	1150.192 ± 0.033
KRISS	Not measured	1038.163 ± 0.058	1079.799 ± 0.058	Not measured	1020.330 ± 0.058	1021.902 ± 0.058	1131.274 ± 0.058	Not measured

5.3 Procedure for calculating the reference value of the dynamic viscosity: χ^2 -test (chi-squared test) and weighted mean

The validation of the results of the pipe viscometers is analysed according to the rules of an intercomparison of laboratories, which not only describes the calculation of the reference value, but also defines the consistency check by means of the χ^2 -test [9].

To determine the reference value, the weighted mean was used, using the inverses of the squares of the associated standard uncertainty as weights:

$$y = \frac{x_1/u^2(x_1) + \dots + x_n/u^2(x_n)}{1/u^2(x_1) + \dots + 1/u^2(x_n)} \quad (2)$$

To determine the standard deviation $u(y)$ associated with y :

$$u(y) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{1/u^2(x_1) + \dots + 1/u^2(x_n)}} \quad (3)$$

To identify the overall consistency of the results a chi-squared test was applied to all n calibration results.

$$\chi_{obs}^2 = \frac{(x_1 - y)^2}{u^2(x_1)} + \dots + \frac{(x_n - y)^2}{u^2(x_n)} \quad (4)$$

The degrees of freedom ν are defined as:

$$\nu = n - 1 \quad (5)$$

The consistency check was deemed to be a pass when $\Pr(\chi^2(\nu) > \chi_{obs}^2) < 0.05$

where Pr is the probability.

The calculations were performed in Microsoft Excel using the function CHIINV (probability, degrees, of freedom-1):

$$\chi_{obs}^2 < CHIINV(0.05; \nu) \quad (6)$$

If the consistency check passed, then y was accepted. If it failed, then the results from the laboratory with the largest contribution to χ_{obs}^2 were omitted from the evaluation and the consistency check repeated.

The reference value and its uncertainty are calculated according to:

$$REF = \frac{\sum(LAB/(U_{95}LAB)^2)}{\sum(1/(U_{95}LAB)^2)} \quad (7)$$

$$U_{95}REF = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum\left(\frac{1}{(U_{95}LAB)^2}\right)}} \quad (8)$$

In Table 7, the results considered for the reference value are highlighted in green and the calculated reference values are listed in the last row.

Table 7. Dynamic viscosities measured by the different laboratories and methods at a temperature of 22 °C. The results presented are the values including the expanded measurement uncertainty $U(k=2)$ in the unit mPa·s. The reference value has been determined with the results of the laboratories highlighted in green.

	Liquid A	Liquid B	Liquid C	Liquid D	Liquid E	Liquid F	Liquid G	Liquid H
METAS	0.9706 ± 0.0088	1.276 ± 0.012	1.810 ± 0.017	1.037 ± 0.010	1.110 ± 0.010	1.111 ± 0.011	6.290 ± 0.057	9.418 ± 0.085
RISE	0.959 ± 0.020	1.279 ± 0.026	1.800 ± 0.037	1.056 ± 0.022	1.112 ± 0.023	1.113 ± 0.023	6.33 ± 0.13	9.35 ± 0.19
NEL	0.9742 ± 0.0098	1.263 ± 0.013	1.795 ± 0.018	1.046 ± 0.011	1.123 ± 0.012	1.158 ± 0.012	6.482 ± 0.064	9.57 ± 0.10
NQIS/EIM	0.9722 ± 0.0098	1.280 ± 0.013	1.823 ± 0.019	1.048 ± 0.011	1.119 ± 0.012	1.119 ± 0.012	6.329 ± 0.064	9.405 ± 0.095
IPQ	1.018 ± 0.047	1.327 ± 0.059	1.862 ± 0.078	1.069 ± 0.051	1.144 ± 0.081	1.160 ± 0.053	6.45 ± 0.26	10.11 ± 0.76
KRISS	Not measured	1.277 ± 0.026	1.803 ± 0.036	Not measured	1.107 ± 0.023	1.110 ± 0.023	6.28 ± 0.13	Not measured
Hahn-Schickard	0.898 ± 0.145	1.166 ± 0.042	1.596 ± 0.021	0.902 ± 0.031	0.972 ± 0.042	1.044 ± 0.042	5.014 ± 0.084	7.749 ± 0.085
Reference value (REF2, χ^2 incl.)	0.972 ± 0.005	1.274 ± 0.007	1.809 ± 0.009	1.045 ± 0.006	1.116 ± 0.006	1.115 ± 0.007	6.310 ± 0.038	9.453 ± 0.051

In most cases, the reference value was determined by the results of three micro pipe viscometers and three capillary glass viscometers. The consistency of the measurement results of the different techniques is excellent.

5.4 *En*-Values for the results of the dynamic viscosity of the liquids A - H

The equivalence of the results of each laboratory can be quantified in the form of the *normalised equivalent value (En)* [9-12].

- For the laboratory, where the result is contributing to the reference value REF2:

$$En = \frac{|LAB - REF2|}{\sqrt{(U_{95}LAB)^2 - (U_{95}REF2)^2}} \quad (8)$$

- For the laboratory, where the result is not contributing to the reference value REF2:

$$En = \frac{|LAB - REF2|}{\sqrt{(U_{95}LAB)^2 + (U_{95}REF2)^2}} \quad (9)$$

Table 8: *En*-Values for the laboratories performed the measurements of the dynamic viscosity.

	Liquid A	Liquid B	Liquid C	Liquid D	Liquid E	Liquid F	Liquid G	Liquid H
METAS	0.19	0.19	0.09	0.95	0.71	0.48	0.48	0.51
RISE	0.67	0.18	0.26	0.58	0.18	0.09	0.13	0.58
NEL	0.28	1.07	0.90	0.17	0.74	3.29	2.36	1.41
NQIS/EIM	0.03	0.50	0.88	0.42	0.33	0.46	0.39	0.61
IPQ	1.04	0.95	0.71	0.50	0.36	0.90	0.58	0.93
KRISS	n/a	0.09	0.18	n/a	0.43	0.25	0.23	n/a
Hahn-Schickard	0.47	2.39	8.42	3.95	3.03	1.60	11.59	14.91

The interpretation of the absolute value of the *En*-Value is as follows:

- $En < 1.0$: the result of the laboratory is consistent with the reference value (green).
- $1.0 < En \leq 1.2$: the result of the laboratory is not clearly consistent with the reference value (orange). A warning is issued. Measurement procedure and uncertainty must be checked.
- $1.2 < En$: the result of the laboratory is inconsistent with the reference value and the reason must be identified (red).

The measurement results of the pipe viscometers show consistent results with the reference values in most cases. NEL is inconsistent with the reference value for the liquids F, G and H. It should be mentioned here that NEL has performed the measurements with the liquids A – E in a first stage and that the liquids F – G were measured in a later stage.

Overall, the performed validation of the pipe viscometers shows a large consistency with well-established measurement methods for the measurement of kinematic viscosity or dynamic viscosity. Capillary glass viscometers are widely used and their method is well-established worldwide for traceable measurement of the kinematic viscosity to the SI units. However, this technique does not allow the in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity in flow applications, which is important for the process-oriented information on the dynamic viscosity of the liquid. The micro pipe viscometers enable the characterization of liquids under flow conditions and the direct calibration of devices that measure dynamic viscosity under flow conditions or the investigation of the influence of dynamic viscosity on the performance of flow devices.

The laboratories with inconsistent results of the En -Value need to investigate the reasons for this and also check the uncertainty value as well as the measurement stability of the pipe viscometer, where the temperature and pressure stability play an important role.

5.5 Deviations of the results of the dynamic viscosity with respect to the reference value for each laboratory

To get a better idea of the deviations of the results of the individual laboratories from the reference value, the deviations with the corresponding uncertainties for each laboratory and liquid are listed in Table 9 and shown in Figure 5.

Table 9: Deviations and uncertainties of each laboratory compared to the reference value in the unit % after the χ^2 -test evaluation.

	Liquid A	Liquid B	Liquid C	Liquid D	Liquid E	Liquid F	Liquid G	Liquid H
METAS	-0.13 ± 0.90	0.14 ± 0.90	0.07 ± 0.90	-0.69 ± 0.90	-0.53 ± 0.90	-0.32 ± 0.90	-0.32 ± 0.90	-0.37 ± 0.90
RISE	-1.29 ± 2.00	0.36 ± 2.00	-0.50 ± 2.00	1.13 ± 2.00	-0.34 ± 2.00	-0.17 ± 2.00	0.26 ± 2.00	-1.12 ± 2.00
NEL	0.24 ± 1.00	-0.91 ± 1.00	-0.77 ± 1.00	0.15 ± 1.00	0.64 ± 1.00	3.81 ± 1.00	2.72 ± 1.00	1.19 ± 1.00
NQIS/EIM	0.03 ± 1.00	0.43 ± 1.00	0.75 ± 1.00	0.35 ± 1.00	0.28 ± 1.00	0.37 ± 1.00	0.31 ± 1.00	-0.51 ± 1.00
IPQ	4.70 ± 4.55	4.14 ± 4.41	2.95 ± 4.17	2.38 ± 4.77	2.49 ± 7.02	4.04 ± 4.52	2.23 ± 3.93	6.95 ± 7.52
KRISS	n/a	0.18 ± 2.00	-0.34 ± 2.00	n/a	-0.84 ± 2.00	-0.48 ± 2.00	-0.45 ± 2.00	n/a
Hahn-Schickard	-7.66 ± 16.1	-8.52 ± 3.52	-11.79 ± 1.30	-13.69 ± 3.43	-12.96 ± 4.25	-6.37 ± 3.93	-20.54 ± 1.67	-18.02 ± 1.08
Reference value (REF2)	0 ± 0.54	0 ± 0.52	0 ± 0.51	0 ± 0.54	0 ± 0.52	0 ± 0.60	0 ± 0.60	0 ± 0.53

Figure 5: Results for the deviations of the dynamic viscosity measurements performed by the different laboratories compared to the reference value. METAS (red circle), RISE (blue square), NEL (green triangle up), EIM (violet triangle down), IPQ (orange triangle left), KRIS (dark yellow triangle right), reference value (black diamond). The deviations of Hahn-Schickard are not shown in the figure as the deviations are larger than the selected range.

6 Conclusion

The measurements of the dynamic viscosity of the eight liquids A – H reported here have shown that the pipe viscometers are a valuable primary standard for the in-line determination of the dynamic viscosity of liquids.

In most cases, the measurement results of the pipe viscometers show consistent results with the reference values determined by the results of the pipe viscometers and well-established measurement methods for the kinematic viscosity or the dynamic viscosity. Capillary glass viscometers are widely used and their method is well-established worldwide for traceable measurement of the kinematic viscosity to the SI units. However, this technique does not allow in-line measurement of dynamic viscosity in flow applications, which is important for the process-oriented information about the dynamic viscosity of the liquid. The micro pipe viscometers enable the characterization of liquids under flow conditions and the direct calibration of devices that measure dynamic viscosity under flow conditions or the investigation of the influence of the dynamic viscosity on the performance of flow devices.

The cases where the En -Value shows inconsistencies must be investigated. The calculation of the measurement uncertainty as well as measurement stability of the pipe viscometer, where temperature and pressure stability play an important role, must be checked and adjusted if needed. NEL is inconsistent with the reference value for the liquids F, G and H.

At this point it should be mentioned that the pipe viscometers were developed as part of the project and the intercomparison was performed more on a technical basis to gain knowledge on the performance of the pipe viscometers. However, the objective of the development of pipe viscometers was also to achieve a measurement uncertainty lower than 2 % ($k=2$). Therefore, the development and the validation of the pipe viscometers have been carried out with success. Some minor adjustments are required to meet the validation criteria and confirm the stated uncertainties lower than 2 %.

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